

Study of Conformational Preferences of Aromatic Functional Groups by Dipole Moments

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The methoxy group of anisole has been shown to prefer a coplanar orientation with the benzene ring by microwave¹, ir² and Raman spectroscopy³. In a compound like *m*-nitroanisole its molecules get

significant contribution from resonance structures like **1a**–**1c** and the C₁–C₂ bond has a high double bond character.

It is of interest to know whether the conformational preference of the methoxy group is *cis* (1d) or *trans* (1e) to the bond of higher double bond character. If it is the former, the calculated dipole moment from group moments for free rotation of groups should be more than the observed dipole moment, and if it is the latter, it should be less. For equal preference the observed moment should agree with the calculated moment. The values given in Table 1 show that 1d is the preferred conformation. The same should be the case for *m*-acetylanisole (2) and *m*-methylsulphonylanisole (3). Similar should be the conformational preference of the OH group in the corresponding phenols (4-6).

A comparison of the calculated and observed dipole moments of 2-6 (Table 1) shows that the observed dipole moments are lower than the calculated ones in all cases, indicating that the preferred conformation is the one in which the OCH₃ or OH group is *cis* to the *ortho*-position with higher double bond character. In these preferential conformations the nonbonding oxygen *p*-orbital is *trans* to the aromatic bond of higher π -electron density.

The conformation of COCH₃ group in *m*-nitroacetophenone, that of CHO group in *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and that of COOH group in *m*-nitro- and *m*-methylsulphonylbenzoic acids were also examined in a similar way.

In these compounds (7-10) the double bond of the C=O of COCH₃, CHO or COOH group is *s-trans* to the aromatic bond of higher double bond character, as found from the data given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF COMPOUNDS HAVING GROUPS WITH PREFERRED CONFORMATION

Sl. no.	Compd.	μ_{calc} D	μ_{obs} D
1.	<i>m</i> -Nitroanisole	4.32	3.89 ^a
2.	<i>m</i> -Acetylanisole	3.24	2.88 ^b
3.	<i>m</i> -Methylsulphonylanisole	4.92	4.77 ^c
4.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	4.22	3.90 ^c 3.93 ^d
5.	<i>m</i> -Acetylphenol	3.30	2.96 ^b
6.	<i>m</i> -Methylsulphonylphenol	4.92	4.10 ^e
7.	<i>m</i> -Nitroacetophenone	4.18	3.57 ^e
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	3.91	3.32 ^e
9.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	4.16	3.50 ^e
10.	<i>m</i> -Methylsulphonylbenzoic acid	4.86	4.53 ^e

^aRef. 14. ^bRef. 15. ^cRef. 16. ^dRef. 17. ^eRef. 18.

In this context it will be of interest to compare the observed and calculated dipole moments of compounds in which the groups have no preferred conformations. Such compounds are listed in Table 2. For all of them the observed moments are in excellent agreement with the calculated moments. This fact reinforces the view that certain aromatic functional groups have a preferential conformation when dissimilar resonance contributions of the aromatic ring arise due to the presence of another group which can strongly conjugate with the benzene ring. The findings of the present study are in conformity with the preferential conformations of OCH_3 and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups detected by Nuclear Overhauser effect difference spectroscopy and relaxation techniques by Kruse *et al.*⁴ in certain aromatic systems.

TABLE 2—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF COMPOUNDS HAVING GROUPS WITH NO PREFERRED CONFORMATION

Sl. no.	Compd.	$\mu_{\text{calc.}}$ D	μ_{obs} D
1.	<i>m</i> -Nitrochlorobenzene	3.15	3.43 ^a 3.44 ^b
2.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobromobenzene	3.45	3.44 ^c
3.	<i>m</i> -Nitroiodobenzene	3.48	3.47 ^d
4.	<i>m</i> -Trifluoromethylchlorobenzene	2.24	2.22 ^e
5.	<i>m</i> -Trifluoromethylfluorobenzene	2.21	2.19 ^e
6.	<i>m</i> -Bromobenzoic acid	2.20	2.17 ^f
7.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenol	2.23	2.19 ^g
8.	<i>m</i> -Dibromobenzene	1.55	1.57 ^h
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorofluorobenzene	1.51	1.52 ⁱ

^aRef. 19. ^bRef. 20. ^cRef. 21. ^dRef. 22. ^eRef. 23.
^fRef. 13. ^gRef. 17. ^hRef. 24. ⁱRef. 25.

For the calculation of dipole moments from group moments by vector addition, the moments of NO_2 , COCH_3 , OCH_3 , F, Cl, Br and I were taken as those⁵ of nitrobenzene (3.95 D), acetophenone (2.90 D), anisole (1.25 D), fluorobenzene (1.43 D), chlorobenzene (1.57 D), bromobenzene (1.55 D) and iodobenzene (1.36 D), respectively. The group moments of SO_2CH_3 , OH, CHO, COOH and CF_3 were taken as those of methyl sulphone (4.65 D)⁶, phenol (1.55 D)⁷, benzaldehyde (2.97 D)⁸, benzoic acid (1.72 D)⁹ and trifluoromethylbenzene (2.56 D)¹⁰, respectively. The angles which the moments of OCH_3 , COCH_3 , OH and CHO groups make with their axes of rotation (the axes being directed towards the group) are 105° ⁶, 55° ¹¹, 92° ¹² and 39° ⁸, respectively. The dipole angle of SO_2CH_3 group

was found to be 49° (calculated from the dipole moments of *m*-chlorophenyl methyl sulphone, 4.39 D⁶, chlorobenzene, 1.57 D⁵ and methyl phenyl sulphone, 4.65 D)⁶ and that of COOH group 79° (calculated from the dipole moments of *m*-chlorobenzoic acid, 2.22 D¹³, benzoic acid, 1.72 D⁹ and chlorobenzene, 1.57 D⁵).

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